

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN WORKLOAD AND MISSED NURSING CARE

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Quality care, workload, staff shortage, missed nursing care, patient health, patient care, and patient psychological support

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Abstract

Aim: The study's aim is to determine how much work is having an impact on patient health and care quality. **Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among the 254 staff nurses at Jinnah Hospital Lahore. The convenient sample technique was used. The population that is targeted was staff nurses of the Jinnah Hospital Lahore. **Results:** The overall result of this study is shown that workload affect on the nursing care and patient health. The Cronbach alpha, Bartlett's, KMO and Kolmogorov-smirnov test values has been checked to insure the validity and reliability in our context. The values shows positive and significant result and tools were considered as reliable and valid for performing statistical analysis. **Conclusion:** The finding demonstrated significant association between workload and missed nursing care. We observed that the workload leads to missed nursing care in the patient bedside.

INTRODUCTION

Workload has been reported to lead nurses to omit required nursing care. In Pakistan, Volume of work influences the quality of the patient's nursing care. There are just 75,000 nurses in Pakistan out of a total population of 227,000,663. There are just 75,000 employees available to serve 200 million people (1). Shortage of staffing leads to increasing the morbidity and mortality rates. Staff shortage is increasing workload in the hospitals. Workload is increasing nurse's burnout in the hospitals. Sometime it leads to missed nursing management in the hospital. It's also effects on the patient-nurse therapeutic relationship(2). Workload may be leads to poor therapeutic relationship between nurse-patient (3). It's also impact on the image of the nurse. For example; now a days in public hospitals, only one or two nurses are serving hundred of patient's at one time in ward. If she's giving care all

patients and neglect one or two patients in ward or not treat them well. Its lead to negative perception of the patient's about the nurse(4). If nurses accomplish her work on short time, its cause exhaustion, stress and depression on the nurse (5).

Because of persistent workload, nurses are working entire shifts without a break or a drink of water(6). According to a survey, eight out of ten nurses have experienced working a full day without even a sip of water, and more than half claim it happens at least once every week. They claimed there wasn't enough staff to allow them to take appropriate breaks or even use the washroom (7).

The workload has led to longer shifts and higher patient-to-nurse ratios. Not only does this undermine the quality of patient care, it can also cause fatigue, injury and stress(8). All of these factors contribute to nurse burnout (9). It's also increase the infection,

forgetting the Aseptic techniques, increase nosocomial infection, maternity death rate and children death rate. Workload is also imparted to distress, cynicism and depression on nurse's shoulders(10). This is the reason; they are less concentrate to focus on their duties, medication and proper care giving to the patient. It also leads to medication errors on bedside (11).

In the Pakistan Public Hospital, 1 to every 3 bed patients complaint about their improper IV cannulation, because workload is lead to missed nursing care in the hospitals. A nurse has a lot of work to do in the ward. When they are doing medication on the bed side, so their focus onto demonstrate their medication quickly and forgotten the changing cannula during medication. But a good nurse, their focus to perform their work on timely. So when they are administrating medicine the patient, they do not change IV cannulation every day. They are giving normal saline push to the patient cannula for the removing blood clot in the vein. A push remove the blockage of the cannula temporarily and save the time of the nurses but its lead to infection. Nurses are changing the dressing of patients, but they are not change the IV cannulation on daily basis. It's lead infection to the patient's (12). Burnout is a significant issue in the social sciences, particularly in the field of health(13), and it is frequently linked to nurses' intentions to leave their line of work. Burnout is a condition of prolonged emotional, physical, and mental tiredness brought on by a mismatch between the demands of the job and the worker's resources. Workload is one of the factors contributing to the worrisome rise in nursing burnout (14). Workload can be qualitative (relating to the kind of abilities and/or effort required to do work tasks) or quantitative (pertaining to the quantity of work to be done and the pace at which it must be completed)

The increase nurse patient ratio effect the patient care outcome such as adequate quality of care, its decreasing the rate of medication error(15), it help in

decreases missed nursing care, and help to build-up therapeutic relationship, providing proper back care and decreasing the rates of pressure injury, help to provide proper hygiene of patient and using aseptic techniques(16), decreasing nosocomial infection in the hospitals, nurses are able to perform proper segregation of the wastages, iv cannulation change in adequate time, nurse able to listen patient problems , use critical thinking to solve them and decision making. Secondly, it's also affect on nurse's health (17).

On the other hand, the decrease in nursing staff there will increase in the rate of nosocomial infection because of inappropriate use of aseptic technique due to workload. Similarly, improper wound care, back care and increasing pressure injuries in the bed ridden patients(18), haven't enough time to buildup the therapeutic relationship between patient and nurse, its affect the image of the nurse, increasing the risk to patient collapses, prolonged iv cannulation infection, improper segregation of wastages, not enough time to listen patient problems, use critical thinking and decision making (19).

The advantages of the decreasing nurses staff in the hospitals. For example; its only lead to take work from minimum staff with maximum work, providing the improper care instead the quality of care, it provides the profit of the system (20).

Material and methodology

Descriptive cross sectional research study design will be used. The study setting will include the staff nurses of Jinnah Hospital Lahore. The study will take approximately nine months. The study targeted population will be the staff nurses of public Hospital (Jinnah Hospital Lahore). The sample size will be calculated by Slovin's formula. Purposive sampling technique will be used to gather information. The staff nurses of the Jinnah hospital will be include in this study. Nurses with age group <24 to 54 will be included in the study.

Analysis and interpretation

Demographic Variables

Table: 01

Table no 1 show that total no of population in this study, those with age group <24 years were 65 (25.6%), those with the age group 25-34years were 110 (43.3%), those with the age group 35-44 years were 49 (19.3%), and those having age group 45-54 years were only 30 (11.8%), majority with the age group 25-34years were 110 (43.3%). Those male nurses were 7 (2.8%) and female nurse 247 (97.2%). From total no of participants majority were female 247 (97.2%). General Nurses were 121 (44.3%), those who were Bs N 131 (48.40%), and those who were MsN 21 (7.7%). From total no of the participants was BsN 131 (48.40%)

	Frequency	Cumulative frequency
Age		
<24	65	25.6
25-34 years	110	68.9
35-44 years	49	88.2
45-54 years	30	100.0
Gender		
Male	7	2.8
Female	247	100.0
Qualification		
General nursing	121	44.3
BsN	131	92.3
MsN	21	100.0

Table no. 2

Table no 2 shows that total no of participants who responded to this question 'Full documentation of all necessary data' those who respond were strongly disagree 34(13.4%), disagree 58 (36.2%), neutral 8 (39%), strongly agree 96 (100.0%), and agree 58 (62%). "IV site care and assessment according to hospital policy" those who respond strongly disagree were 10(3.9%),disagree 19 (11.4%), neutral were 21(19.7%), strongly agree were 79 (50.8%), agreed were 125 (100.0%)."Monitoring intake/output" those who respond strongly disagree 31(12.2%), disagree 61(36.2%), neutral 18(43.3%), strongly agree 92 (100.0%) and agree 52 (63.8%). "Vital signs assessed as ordered" those who respond were strongly disagree 26 (10.2%), disagree 85 (43.7%), neutral 11(48.0%), strongly agree 82 (100.0%) and agree 50 (67.7%). "Focused reassessment according to patient" those who respond strongly disagree were 44(17.3%), disagree 84(50.4%), neutral 37 (65.0%), strongly agree 53(100.0%) and agree 36 (79.1%).

	Frequency	Cumulative frequency
Full documentation of all necessary data		
Strongly disagree	34	13.4
Disagree	58	36.2
Neutral	8	39.4
Strongly agree	96	100.0
Agree	58	62.2
IV site care and assessment according to hospital policy		
Strongly disagree	10	3.9
Disagree	19	11.4
Neutral	21	19.7

Strongly agree	79	50.8
Agree	125	100.0
Monitoring intake/output		
Strongly disagree	31	12.2
Disagree	61	36.2
Neutral	18	43.3
Strongly agree	92	100.0
Agree	52	63.8
Vital signs assessed as ordered		
Strongly disagree	26	10.2
Disagree	85	43.7
Neutral	11	48.0
Strongly agree	82	100.0
Agree	50	67.7
Focused reassessment according to patient		
Strongly disagree	44	17.3
Disagree	84	50.4
Neutral	37	65.0
Strongly agree	53	100.0
Agree	36	79.1

Table no.3

Table no 2 shows that total no of participants who responded to this question “hand washing” those who respond strongly disagree 42(16.5%), disagree 79(47.6%), neutral 27(58.3%), strongly agree 69(100.0%), and agree 37(72.8%). “Bedside glucose monitoring as ordered” those respond strongly disagree 25 (9.8%), disagree 90(45.3%), neutral 22(53.9%), strongly agree 59 (100.0%) and agree 58(76.8%). “Patient assessments performed each shift” those who respond strongly disagree 9 (3.5%), disagree 44(20.9%), neutral 47(39.4%), strongly agree 92 (100.0%) and agree 62 (63.8%). “Assess effectiveness of medications” those who respond strongly disagree 16(6.3%), disagree 45(24.0%), neutral 10(28.0%), strongly agree 91(100.0%) and agree 92(64.2%). “PRN medication requests acted on within five minutes” those who respond were strongly disagree 23(9.1%), disagree 100(48.4%), neutral 15(54.3%), strongly agree 72 (100.0%) and agree 44(71.7%).

	Frequency	Cumulative frequency
Hand washing		
Strongly disagree	42	16.5
Disagree	79	47.6
Neutral	27	58.3
Strongly agree	69	100.0
Agree	37	72.8
Bedside glucose monitoring as ordered		
Strongly disagree	25	9.8
Disagree	90	45.3
Neutral	22	53.9
Strongly agree	59	100.0
Agree	58	76.8
Patient assessments performed each shift		

Strongly disagree	9	3.5
Disagree	44	20.9
Neutral	47	39.4
Strongly agree	92	100.0
Agree	62	63.8
Assess effectiveness of medications		
Strongly disagree	16	6.3
Disagree	45	24.0
Neutral	10	28.0
Strongly agree	91	100.0
Agree	92	64.2
PRN medication requests acted on within five minutes		
Strongly disagree	23	9.1
Disagree	100	48.4
Neutral	15	54.3
Strongly agree	72	100.0
Agree	44	71.7

DISCUSSION OF RESULT FINDING

The descriptive cross sectional research study was examining “Association between workload and missed nursing care”. The study result shows that total respondents who respond in this study to the majority were female. The tool used for “Association between workload and missed nursing care” was adopted. Those who were The KMO, Bartlett’s test and Cronbach alpha values has been checked to ensure the validity and reliability in our context. The values shows positive and significant result and tools were considered as reliable and valid for performing statistically analysis. Descriptive analysis shows that from total participants who respond, with the age group <24 years were 65 (25.6%), those with the age group 25-34years were 110 (43.3%), those with the age group 35-44 years were 49 (19.3%), and those having age group 45-54 years were only 30 (11.8%), majority with the age group 25-34years were 110 (43.3%). Those male nurses were 7 (2.8%) and female nurse 247 (97.2%). From total no of participants majority were female 247 (97.2%). General Nurses were 121 (44.3%), those who were Bs N 131 (48.40%), and those who were MsN 21 (7.7%). From total no of the participants was BsN 131 (48.40%) Data normality also checked. Total participants who respond about question “full documentation of all necessary data” from who

respond strongly disagree with this question are 34 (13.4%), those who respond disagree about this question are 58 (22.8%), those who respond neutral about this question are 8 (3.1%), those who were agree with this question are 58 (22.8), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 96 (37.8%). Majority of the participants were strongly agree about this question. From total participants who respond about question “IV site care and assessment according to hospital policy”. From those who respond strongly disagree with this question are 10 (3.9%), those who respond disagree with this question are 19 (7.5%), those who respond neutral with this question are 21 (8.3%), those who respond agree with this question are 78 (31.1%), and those who respond strongly agree with this question are 125 (49.2%). Majority of the population were strongly agreed with this question. From total participants who respond about question “Monitoring intake/output” from total no of participants who respond strongly disagree about this question are 31 (12.2%), those who respond disagree about this question are 61 (24.0%), those who respond neutral about this question are 18 (7.1%), those who respond agree about this question are 20.5, those who respond agree about this question are 52 (20.5%), and those who respond strongly agree are 92 (36.2%). Majority of the population was

strongly agree are 92 (36.2%). From total no of participants who respond about question “Vital signs assessed as ordered” Those who respond strongly disagree about this question are 26 (10.2%), those who respond disagree with this question are 85 (33.5%), those who respond neutral about this question are 11 (4.3%), those who respond agree about this question are 50 (19.7%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 82 (32.3%). Majority of the participants respond disagree about this question. From total participants who respond about question “Focused reassessment according to patient” those who responded strongly disagree about this question are 44 (17.3%), those who respond disagree about this question are 84 (33.1%), those who respond neutral about this question are 37 (14.6%), those who respond agree about this question are 36 (14.2%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 53 (20.9%). Majority of the population respond disagree about this question. From total participants who respond about question “Hand washing” those who respond strongly disagree with this question are 42 (16.5%), those who respond disagree about this question are 79 (31.1%), those who respond neutral about this question are 27 (10.6%), those who respond agree about this question are 37 (14.6%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 69 (27.2%). Majority of population respond disagree about this question. From total participants who respond about question “Bedside glucose monitoring as ordered” those who respond strongly disagree this question are 25 (9.8%), those who respond agree about this question are 90 (35.4%), those who respond neutral about this question are 22 (8.7%), those who respond agree about this question are 58 (22.8), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 58 (23.2%). Majority of the population respond agree about this question are 90 (35.4%). From total participants who respond about question “Patient assessments performed each shift” those who respond strongly agree about this question are 9 (3.5%), those who respond disagree about this question are 44 (17.3%), those who respond neutral about this question are 47 (18.5%), those who respond agree about this question are 62 (24.4%), those who respond agree about this question are 62

(24.4%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 92 (36.2%). Majority of the population respond agree about this question (36.2%). From total participants who respond about question “Assess effectiveness of medications” those who respond strongly disagree about this question are 16 (6.3%), those who respond disagree about this question are 45 (17.7%), those who respond neutral about this question are 10 (3.9%), those who respond agree about this question are 92 (36.2%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 91 (35.8%). Majority of the population respond agree 92 (36.2%). From total participants who respond about question “PRN medication requests acted on within five minutes” those who respond strongly disagree about this question are 23 (9.1%), those who respond disagree about this question are 100 (39.4%), those who respond neutral about this question 15 (5.9%), those who respond agree about this question are 44 (17.3%), and those who respond strongly agree about this question are 72 (28.3%). Majority of the population respond disagree 100 (39.4%).

5.1 CONCLUSION

The finding demonstrated significant association between staff shortage and missed nursing care. We observed that the staff shortage leads workload on the nurse shoulders and causing stress and exhaustion. Workload is the main reason of the missed nursing care on the patient bedside. Its affect to increase the patient dissatisfaction, morbidity, mortality rates, sudden death, nosocomial infection, maternal and neonatal death.

5.2 LIMITATION

1. A descriptive cross-sectional study design is used to check the effect of the workload on patient health and quality of care.
2. The total population is very low so the sample size is also low because we target the nurse’s of one hospital.
3. The convenient sampling technique will be used in the research study which gave biasness on results.
4. During conducting my study there are following limitations, like lack of resources, shortage

of time, and data collect by convenient technique which gave biasness on results.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION

The study recommendation that the future researchers work on the highlighted factors which the current study has examined.

Future researchers can use more than two organizations that there result will be generalizable.

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